

AN ATOMISTIC STUDY OF CREEP BEHAVIOR IN FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite has been increasingly used in civil engineering field. The durability of CFRP composite is highly dependent on the interfacial integrity between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix. During the long-term service-life, the composite is inevitably subject to external loading, which causes the creep between fiber and matrix. As interfacial creep occurs, especially under the severe loading, it leads to the variation in the local interfacial region, which affects the CFRP composite durability. However, it is still not clear about how the microstructure of fiber/matrix interface changes during the creep, which impedes a complete understanding of the interfacial deterioration in CFRP composite. In this study, the creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface is investigated by using molecular dynamics simulations. The molecular interface model is constructed by bonding the epoxy molecule to the graphite sheets representing the fiber outer-layer. To simulate the interfacial creep, the graphite sheets are subject to the pull-out simulations at different load levels. It is found that there exists a threshold stress between 32.03 MPa and 35.23 MPa. Specifically, at stress levels below 32.03 MPa, the strain of graphite sheets increases slightly and reaches a constant value at the end of the loading, where the graphite sheets closely attach to the strained epoxy molecule and no interfacial detachment between epoxy and graphite sheets is observed. Meanwhile, at stress level above 35.23 MPa, the strain of graphite sheets undergoes a rapid increase as the sliding between the graphite sheets and epoxy proceeds rapidly, which leads to the interfacial detachment between epoxy and graphite sheets. This study provides nanoscale insights into the creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface, which contributes to the understanding of long-term interfacial integrity of CFRP composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the excellent mechanical properties including low density, high stiffness and strength, and excellent fatigue resistance, carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite has been increasingly used in civil engineering field, such as the reinforcement and strengthening of deteriorated and new infrastructures, and all-composite structural systems [1-3]. The performance of macroscopic CFRP composite is highly dependent on the interfacial integrity between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix, as the interface region governs the interaction and stress transfer between bonded materials [4-9]. During the long-term service-life, it is inevitable that the composite is subject to external load, which results in the shear forces in the interfacial region [10]. The constant shear loading consequently leads to the sliding between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix, which is denoted as the interfacial creep [11]. As the creep continues, it can finally lead to fiber intrusion or protrusion associated with matrix, which deteriorates the interfacial bonding and macroscopic properties of CFRP composite [12]. In order to

fully understand the interfacial deterioration in CFRP, it requires a fundamental understanding of the creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface under sustained loading.

Previous experimental studies have been carried out to investigate the interfacial creep behavior between fiber and matrix under constant loading conditions [13-16]. The macroscopic composite sample was subject to push-out tests to investigate the interfacial creep, where the epoxy matrix was fixed by a holder and the single fiber was pushed out under the applied external stress, as shown in Fig. 1(a) [13-15]. After loading for up to 30 minutes, the displacement of carbon fiber shows a linear relationship with the load ranging from 10 mN to 25 mN, while the fiber displacement increases more rapidly when the load is higher than 25 mN, which reveals that the increasing load leads to the rapid displacement of fiber and the more severe weakening of interface [15]. Further investigation focuses on the local interfacial creep behavior between a matrix droplet and a single fiber, as shown in Fig. 1(b) [16]. The interfacial creep tests were performed by using fiber pull-out tests, where the end of the single fiber is subject to the static loads up to 300 mN for 2 minutes. Specifically, at the load of 150 mN, the strain of the fiber shows an almost linear increment with the loading time and reaches the constant level after loading for 2 minutes, while the strain increases rapidly at 300mN and the interfacial debonding is observed [16]. From these experimental studies, it is demonstrated that the interfacial creep caused by sustained loading is often related to the deteriorated interfacial integrity, especially at high loading levels, which degrades the composite performance. However, there is still a lack of microscopic information about the creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface, which impedes the complete understanding of the creep behavior.

Fig. 1: The multi-scale creep test of the composite sample: (a) the push-out tests for the macroscopic composite sample where the epoxy matrix was fixed by the holder and the single fiber was pushed out at the applied external stress; (b) the pull-out tests for the sample where the fiber was pulled out from the matrix droplet under the static loading; and (c) the pull-out tests for the nanoscale interface model consisting of epoxy molecule bonded to graphite sheets representing the fiber outer-layer.

To obtain a comprehensive understanding of the interfacial deterioration in CFRP composite, it is essential to observe how the microstructure of fiber/matrix interface changes during the creep. Recently, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation has been increasingly used to examine interfacial structural changes at nanoscale [17-23], which can help understand the interfacial creep behavior at atomistic level. The interface model consisting of epoxy molecule bonded to graphite layers is considered as the representative model of fiber/matrix interface at nanoscale, as shown in Fig. 1(c). In previous simulation study, the formation of carbon fiber/matrix interface is investigated, where the interfacial thickness is found to be around 1 nm, which is consistent with the transmission electron microscope observation of the interfacial region [24]. Further interfacial study has been carried out to study interfacial shear properties of fiber/matrix interface, as the shear property is strongly related to the interfacial creep resistance. By pulling out the graphite substrate with a constant velocity of $50 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, the interfacial shear stress is determined to be $34.4\pm 1.4 \text{ MPa}$, which is consistent with the single

fiber fragmentation testing results [25]. This value characterizes the threshold stress that can lead to the fiber detachment [26]. Despite the previous MD simulation studies on structures and properties of fiber/matrix interface, the microscopic interfacial behavior during the creep process is still unknown.

This paper focuses on the understanding of the creep behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy interface at different load levels. Molecular interface model consisting of epoxy molecule bonded to graphite sheets is constructed to represent the fiber/matrix interface at nanoscale. By pulling out the graphite sheets at different load levels, the interfacial creep is simulated. During the pull-out process, the displacement of graphite sheets are recorded, which is used to quantify the resistance of fiber/matrix interface under the creep loading. By observing the molecular interfacial behavior during pulling process, interfacial creep behavior between graphite sheets and epoxy molecules is examined, which helps understand the interfacial creep behavior. The simulation results reported in this study provide atomistic information of the interfacial creep behavior between the carbon fiber and epoxy matrix, which contributes to the understanding of the interfacial deterioration in CFRP composite.

2 SIMULATION DETAILS

To characterize atomistic interactions, the consistent valence force field (CVFF) is adopted, which has been used to study fiber/matrix interfacial properties in previous studies [27-30]. In CVFF potential, bonded interactions include two-body bond stretching, three-body angle bending, and four-body dihedral angle torsions, while non-bonded interactions include van de Waals (vdW) and Coulombic interactions. Specifically, the cutoff distance for vdW and short-range Coulombic interactions is set to 1 nm, while long-range Coulombic interactions are calculated using particle-particle-particle-mesh solver. Partial charges of the atoms are calculated by using bond increment approach [18, 26].

In the modeling of molecular interface model, the epoxy molecule is formed by the cross-linking process between the monomers consisting of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether, the basic structure of epoxy in CFRP composite [26]. The cross-linking process of epoxy is achieved by using a computational algorithm, which has been used extensively in modeling the epoxy network in recent simulation works [18-22]. The constructed epoxy model is shown in Fig. 2, with the initial dimensions of 4.0 nm \times 4.0 nm \times 5.0 nm. The thickness of around 5 nm is larger than the cutoff distance of the non-bonded interactions, which can eliminate the influence of the upper-surface epoxy molecule on the local interfacial interaction [25, 26, 31]. The density of the epoxy model is measured as 1.18 g \cdot cc $^{-1}$, which shows a good agreement with the available value in the range of 1.07-1.20 g \cdot cc $^{-1}$ [18-20]. Meanwhile, Young's modulus of the epoxy model is around 4 GPa, which agrees with previous experimental tensile test measurements [32-34]. Therefore, the molecular model generated here is considered as the reasonable model for the epoxy matrix. For the carbon fiber surface, the outer-layer is composed of graphene crystallites with parallel graphite sheets in size of nanometers [35]. In previous MD studies, several parallel graphite layers are used to represent the carbon fiber surface [17, 26]. Here, the five-layer graphite sheets are used to represent the carbon fiber outer-layer, as shown in Fig. 2. The five-layer graphite sheets have a thickness of 1.4 nm, which is larger than the cutoff distance of 1 nm to eliminate the effect of the bottom layer on the interactions of the interface. Each graphite layer has the initial lateral dimensions of 7.6 nm \times 7.7 nm and is terminated with hydrogen atoms in the two lateral dimensions. The graphite sheets are placed in the center of the simulation cell and the cross-linked epoxy molecule is placed on top of the graphite sheets to generate the epoxy layer, as shown in Fig. 2. The periodic conditions are applied to the simulation cell with the dimension of 100.0 nm \times 100.0 nm \times 100.0 nm. The lengths in all directions are sufficiently large to eliminate the effect of the mirror images on the interaction of the interface [21].

Fig. 2: Molecular structure of fiber/matrix interface consisting of epoxy molecule bonded to graphite sheets. The carbon atoms are drawn in silver, the oxygen atoms are drawn in red, and the hydrogen atoms are drawn in white.

After the model construction, it is subject to equilibration process to relief the stress in the structure. All MD simulations are performed in the open source code LAMMPS with a time step of 1 fs [36]. During the equilibration process, the lowest layer of the graphite sheets is kept fixed and the system is relaxed at NVE ensemble for 500 ps, and then relaxed at NVT ensemble at different temperatures to simulate annealing process, where the temperature is increased from 0 K to 600 K at a rate of 100 K, and then cooled down to 300 K at the same rate. At each temperature, the equilibration process is run for 500 ps. After that, the interface model is relaxed in an NPT ensemble at 300 K and 1 atm for 500 ps. Furthermore, the lowest layer of the graphite sheets is set free and the whole interface is equilibrated in another NPT ensemble at 300 K and 1 atm for 500ps followed by an NVT ensemble at 300 K for 500 ps. Finally, the 25% thickness of the top epoxy molecule is kept fixed to mimic the boundary and the system is subject to another NVT equilibration at 300 K for 500 ps. The Nosé-Hoover thermostat and Barostat are implemented to control the temperature and pressure, respectively [37, 38]. To confirm the equilibration state, the root-mean-square displacement of atoms in the model is examined, which keeps at constant level when the model is fully equilibrated.

After the model is equilibrated, the pull-out simulations are carried out at different load levels to simulate the creep test. Specifically, all the atoms in the graphite sheets are subject to an instantaneous constant force. Given that the graphite sheets are around square, the pull-out simulation is only carried out in x direction, as shown in Fig. 2. The choice of the applied force is based on the deformation of the graphite sheets during the creep simulation, which matches with the range of forces causing the graphite sheets from intact to total pull-out. During the creep at different load levels, the displacements of the graphite sheets are measured and the configuration of the model is captured.

3 DISCUSSION

During the creep simulations, the graphite sheets are subject to the instantaneous constant force at different levels. At each load level, the simulation is finished when the interfacial detachment occurs or it stops after 10 ns run when the displacement of the graphite sheets reaches a stable level, which is close to the timespan of several ns in similar creep simulation [23]. From the displacement-force curve shown in Fig. 3, two regimes are observed based on increasing trend of the maximum displacement with the applied force. In the first regime where the applied force is lower than 1000 pN, the strain is small and increases with the increasing force. In the second regime, where the applied force is above 1100 pN, the interfacial detachment between graphite sheets and epoxy molecule is observed within the simulation timespan. According to the pull-out simulation, it is found that a threshold force exists before the total interfacial detachment, which is in the range of 1000 pN and 1100 pN. The corresponding threshold stress is between 32.03 MPa and 35.23 MPa, which is calculated using the equation $S=F/A$, where F is the applied shearing force, and A is the projected area

of the epoxy molecule in the x - y plane after the equilibration, with a value of 31.22 nm^2 . The predicted threshold stress agrees very well with the simulated interfacial stress of $34.4 \pm 1.4 \text{ MPa}$, as measured from shearing the graphite substrate from the epoxy matrix [25]. Meanwhile, the simulated results are slightly higher than the maximum shear stress of $19.9 \pm 8.1 \text{ MPa}$ obtained from the fiber pull-out test of pultruded carbon/epoxy rod composite [39]. In practice, there are structural voids and defects in the fiber/matrix interface, which degrade the structural integrity and lead to a lower interfacial shear strength of the experimental samples [31]. Meanwhile, the water absorbed in the bonded interface disrupts the molecular interaction, which could also contribute to the lower interfacial shear strength as observed in the experiment [19, 22]. In this paper, the molecular model is free of structural voids and water absorption, which could lead to a slightly higher threshold stress as compared with the macroscopic experiments [23, 25].

Fig. 3: The maximum displacement within simulation timespan as a function of applied force level: two regimes are observed from the curve, with 1000 pN and 1100 pN as a threshold force region between the two regimes.

From our pull-out simulations, no interfacial detachment is observed during the creep when stress is lower than 32.03 MPa , whereas the detachment occurs when stress is above 35.23 MPa . Based on the threshold stress region, the loading is divided into low and high regimes for analyzing the creep response respectively. The strain values as a function of loading time at different stress levels are shown in Fig. 4(a). In the low stress regime, the stress levels of 16.02 MPa , 22.42 MPa , and 28.82 MPa corresponding to the load level of 500 pN , 700 pN , and 900 pN are selected. Within the initial loading, the strain of the graphite sheets increases slightly, and it is the first stage (stage I). During this stage, the graphite sheets attach to the epoxy molecule closely, and the small strain occurs in the epoxy molecule, which is demonstrated by the bending of the epoxy molecule, as shown in Fig. 4(b). After the first stage, the increasing rate of the strain starts to decrease, which is denoted as the second stage (stage II). During this stage, the graphite sheets start to slide along the epoxy surface. The transition between the first and second stages is determined when the first derivative of the strain-time curve starts to decline, which is around 1 ns . As the loading continues, the strain variation becomes stable and reaches a constant value at the end of the loading, where the graphite sheets still attach to the epoxy molecule and no interfacial detachment is observed, as shown in Fig. 4(b). The shape of the strain-time curves shows good agreement with previous experiment at low stress levels, which exhibits the same initial increasing stage and subsequent steady stage without interfacial detachment [15].

(b)
After equilibration

Stage I

Stage II

Detachment

Fig. 4: The (a) strain variation of graphite sheets and (b) corresponding configurational changes of fiber/matrix interface model within the simulation timespan of 10 ns: in the low stress regime of 16.02 MPa, 22.42 MPa and 28.82 MPa, the strain increases slightly at the first stage (stage I), where the

small strain occurs in the epoxy as demonstrated by the bending of the epoxy molecule, and then the increasing rate of the strain starts to decrease at the second stage (stage II), where the graphite sheets start to slide along the epoxy surface; as the loading continues, the strain variation becomes stable and reaches a constant value, where the graphite sheets still attach to the epoxy molecule and no interfacial detachment is observed. At high stress levels of 35.23 MPa, 41.64 MPa, and 48.05 MPa, after the similar first two stages, the final detachment between the graphite sheets and the epoxy occurs, as shown in figure (b).

At high stress levels of 35.23 MPa, 41.64 MPa, and 48.05 MPa corresponding to the load levels of 1100 pN, 1300 pN, and 1500 pN, the interface undergoes similar initial first two stages, where the strain slightly increases at the first stage and then the increasing rate of the strain starts to decrease at the second stage. During the second stage, the sliding between the graphite sheets and epoxy proceeds rapidly, and the final detachment between the graphite sheets and the epoxy is observed, as shown in Fig. 4(b). The simulation time at detached moment is 8.7 ns, 5.5 ns, and 3.8 ns for the three stress levels, respectively. The shorter time at fully detachment indicates the faster pull-out of the graphite sheets with increasing stress level, which coincides with the results of the similar interfacial creep simulation of epoxy-silica interface, where the detachment time shows similar dramatic decrease with an increasing applied stress [23].

Using the pull-out simulations, the creep response and corresponding microstructure change of fiber/matrix interface at different stress levels are investigated at a fundamental atomistic level. Specifically, the interfacial behaviors including epoxy molecule straining and sliding between graphite sheets and epoxy account for the creep response at different stages. It is noted that for all the stress levels, the difference between the first and second stages is mainly resulted from overcoming the interfacial adhesion energy barrier before the graphite sheets start to slide. At low stress levels, the strain reaches a constant value and no interfacial detachment is observed at the end of the 10 ns loading, while at high stress levels, the significant acceleration of sliding of graphite sheets leads to the accelerated strain growth during the second stage and finally leads to the detachment of the graphite sheets. As the simulations conducted here are based on the pristine graphite sheets without considering the surface treatments, the observed creep response may be slightly different for the case using the functionalized graphite sheets representing the treated fiber surface. Meanwhile, during the long-term service-life, the water molecules could diffuse into the epoxy and the fiber/matrix interface, and the structural defects or voids could develop in the bonded interface, which affect the molecular creep response as observed here [31, 40-43]. It is noted that the molecular interfacial creep response and the microstructural variation as observed here represent the most valuable information for understanding the interfacial creep behavior in CFRP composite. In order to investigate the effect of these various factors, it requires a sub-micron scale model of the fiber/matrix interface, which could incorporate the different functional groups onto the graphite sheets, nanoscale structural voids, and suitable diffusion passage of moisture and different ions. It is believed that the strategy described in this study is applicable to the simulation of the larger-scale interface model in the understanding of the effect of fiber surface treatments, structural defects, and humidity on the interfacial creep deformation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the interfacial creep behavior of fiber/matrix interface is studied using molecular dynamics simulations by focusing on the microstructural changes during the creep simulation. The molecular model of fiber/matrix interface is constructed, which is subject to pull-out simulations at different constant load levels. It is found that the creep response of the interface exhibits two distinct regimes under different loadings, and the threshold stress between high and low stress levels is found to be between 32.03 MPa and 35.23 MPa corresponding to the load level of 1000 pN and 1100 pN. At low stress levels, the strain increases slightly at the first stage, and then the increasing rate of the strain starts to decrease at the second stage, and finally reaches a constant value, where the graphite sheets attach to the epoxy molecule. At high stress levels, the strain undergoes similar initial first two stages, but with accelerated sliding movement and detachment occurs at the final state. The simulation results

show the molecular changes of fiber/matrix interface from the onset of creep to the final detachment under different stress levels, including straining of the epoxy molecule and the sliding between graphite sheets and epoxy, which enrich the fundamental understanding of the interfacial creep behavior of the fiber/matrix interface at atomistic level. It is envisioned that based on this work, we can further investigate how the interfacial structure changes, such as functionalized carbon fiber surface, and the environmental conditions including temperature and humidity can affect the threshold stress and creep behavior at the interface in the bonded material system.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V.M. Karbhari, J.W. Chin, D. Hunston, B. Benmokrane, T. Juska, R. Morgan, J.J. Lesko, U. Sorathia and D. Reynaud, Durability gap analysis for fiber-reinforced polymer composites in civil infrastructure, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, **7**, 2003, pp. 238-247 (doi: [10.1061/\(asce\)1090-0268\(2003\)7:3\(238\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)1090-0268(2003)7:3(238))).
- [2] H.R. Hamilton, B. Benmokrane, C.W. Dolan and M.M. Sprinkel, Polymer Materials to Enhance Performance of Concrete in Civil Infrastructure, *Polymer Reviews*, **49**, 2009, pp. 1-24 (doi: [10.1080/15583720802656153](https://doi.org/10.1080/15583720802656153)).
- [3] A.P. Mouritz, E. Gellert, P. Burchill and K. Challis, Review of advanced composite structures for naval ships and submarines, *Composite Structures*, **53**, 2001, pp. 21-41 (doi: [10.1016/s0263-8223\(00\)00175-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0263-8223(00)00175-6)).
- [4] L.C. Hollaway, A review of the present and future utilisation of FRP composites in the civil infrastructure with reference to their important in-service properties, *Construction and Building Materials*, **24**, 2010, pp. 2419-2445 (doi: [10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.04.062](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.04.062)).
- [5] H. He, J.L. Wang, K. Li, J. Wang and J. Gu, Mixed resin and carbon fibres surface treatment for preparation of carbon fibres composites with good interfacial bonding strength, *Materials & Design*, **31**, 2010, pp. 4631-4637 (doi: [10.1016/j.matdes.2010.05.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2010.05.031)).
- [6] E. Moaseri, M. Maghrebi and M. Baniadam, Improvements in mechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites: A microwave-assisted approach in functionalization of carbon fiber via diamines, *Materials & Design*, **55**, 2014, pp. 644-652 (doi: [10.1016/j.matdes.2013.10.040](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2013.10.040)).
- [7] M. Sharma, S. Gao, E. Mäder, H. Sharma, L.Y. Wei and J. Bijwe, Carbon fiber surfaces and composite interphases, *Composites Science and Technology*, **102**, 2014, pp. 35-50 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.07.005)).
- [8] Y. Wang, L. Meng, L. Fan, G. Wu, L. Ma, M. Zhao and Y. Huang, Carboxyl functionalization of carbon fibers via aryl diazonium reaction in molten urea to enhance interfacial shear strength, *Applied Surface Science*, **362**, 2016, pp. 341-347 (doi: [10.1016/j.apsusc.2015.11.232](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2015.11.232)).
- [9] G. Wu, L. Ma, L. Liu, Y. Wang, F. Xie, Z. Zhong, M. Zhao, B. Jiang and Y. Huang, Interface enhancement of carbon fiber reinforced methylphenylsilicone resin composites modified with silanized carbon nanotubes, *Materials & Design*, **89**, 2016, pp. 1343-1349 (doi: [10.1016/j.matdes.2015.10.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2015.10.016)).
- [10] M. Shahidi, B. Pichler and C. Hellmich, How interface size, density, and viscosity affect creep and relaxation functions of matrix-interface composites: a micromechanical study, *Acta Mechanica*, **227**, 2015, pp. 229-252 (doi: [10.1007/s00707-015-1429-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00707-015-1429-9)).
- [11] W.K. Goertzen and M.R. Kessler, Creep behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy matrix composites, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **421**, 2006, pp. 217-225 (doi: [10.1016/j.msea.2006.01.063](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2006.01.063)).

- [12] I. Dutta, K.A. Peterson and C. Park, Interfacial creep in multi-component material systems, *Jom-Journal of the Minerals Metals & Materials Society*, **55**, 2003, pp. 38-43 (doi: [10.1007/s11837-003-0192-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-003-0192-x)).
- [13] S. Zhandarov and E. Mäder, Indirect estimation of fiber/polymer bond strength and interfacial friction from maximum load values recorded in the microbond and pull-out tests. Part II: Critical energy release rate, *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **17**, 2003, pp. 967-980 (doi: [10.1163/156856103322112879](https://doi.org/10.1163/156856103322112879)).
- [14] S.F. Zhandarov, E. Mäder and O.R. Yurkevich, Indirect estimation of fiber/polymer bond strength and interfacial friction from maximum load values recorded in the microbond and pull-out tests. Part I: local bond strength, *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **16**, 2002, pp. 1171-1200 (doi: [10.1163/156856102320256837](https://doi.org/10.1163/156856102320256837)).
- [15] S. Corujeira Gallo, X. Li, Z. Zhang, C. Charitidis and H. Dong, Viscoelastic response of carbon fibre reinforced polymer during push-out tests, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **112**, 2018, pp. 178-185 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.06.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.06.003)).
- [16] S. Zhandarov, E. Pisanova and K. Schneider, Fiber-stretching test: a new technique for characterizing the fiber-matrix interface using direct observation of crack initiation and propagation, *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **14**, 2000, pp. 381-398 (doi: [10.1163/156856100742663](https://doi.org/10.1163/156856100742663)).
- [17] V. Varshney, A.K. Roy and J.W. Baur, Modeling the Role of Bulk and Surface Characteristics of Carbon Fiber on Thermal Conductance across the Carbon-Fiber/Matrix Interface, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **7**, 2015, pp. 26674-26683 (doi: [10.1021/acsami.5b08591](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.5b08591)).
- [18] L.-h. Tam, L. He and C. Wu, Molecular dynamics study on the effect of salt environment on interfacial structure, stress, and adhesion of carbon fiber/epoxy interface, *Composite Interfaces*, 2018, pp. 1-17 (doi: [10.1080/09276440.2018.1506901](https://doi.org/10.1080/09276440.2018.1506901)).
- [19] L.-h. Tam, A. Zhou and C. Wu, Nanomechanical behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy interface in hygrothermal conditioning: A molecular dynamics study, *Materials Today Communications*, 2019, pp. 495-505 (doi: [10.1016/j.mtcomm.2019.04.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2019.04.002)).
- [20] L.-h. Tam, A. Zhou, R. Zhang and C. Wu, Effect of hygrothermal environment on traction-separation behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy interface, *Construction and Building Materials*, 2019, pp. 728-738 (doi: [10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.06.087](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.06.087)).
- [21] L.-h. Tam and D. Lau, Moisture effect on the mechanical and interfacial properties of epoxy-bonded material system: An atomistic and experimental investigation, *Polymer*, **57**, 2015, pp. 132-142 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymer.2014.12.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2014.12.026)).
- [22] L.-h. Tam, C.L. Chow and D. Lau, Moisture effect on interfacial integrity of epoxy-bonded system: a hierarchical approach, *Nanotechnology*, **29**, 2018, pp. 024001 (doi: [10.1088/1361-6528/aa9537](https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/aa9537)).
- [23] W. Jian, L.-h. Tam and D. Lau, Atomistic study of interfacial creep behavior in epoxy-silica bilayer system, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **132**, 2018, pp. 229-236 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2017.09.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2017.09.006)).
- [24] C.M. Hadden, B.D. Jensen, A. Bandyopadhyay, G.M. Odegard, A. Koo and R. Liang, Molecular modeling of EPON-862/graphite composites: Interfacial characteristics for multiple crosslink densities, *Composites Science and Technology*, **76**, 2013, pp. 92-99 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.01.002)).
- [25] B. Demir, K.M. Beggs, B.L. Fox, L. Servinis, L.C. Henderson and T.R. Walsh, A predictive model of interfacial interactions between functionalised carbon fibre surfaces cross-linked with epoxy resin, *Composites Science and Technology*, **159**, 2018, pp. 127-134 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.02.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.02.029)).
- [26] B. Demir, L.C. Henderson and T.R. Walsh, Design Rules for Enhanced Interfacial Shear Response in Functionalized Carbon Fiber Epoxy Composites, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **9**, 2017, pp. 11846-11857 (doi: [10.1021/acsami.6b16041](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.6b16041)).
- [27] Y. Xiao and G. Xian, Effects of moisture ingress on the bond between carbon fiber and epoxy resin investigated with molecular dynamics simulation, *Polymer Composites*, **39**, 2018, pp. E2074-E2083 (doi: [10.1002/pc.24459](https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.24459)).

- [28] S.I. Kundalwal and S. Kumar, Multiscale modeling of stress transfer in continuous microscale fiber reinforced composites with nano-engineered interphase, *Mechanics of Materials*, **102**, 2016, pp. 117-131 (doi: [10.1016/j.mechmat.2016.09.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2016.09.002)).
- [29] P.A. Amnaya, C.L. Dimitris and C.H. Daniel, Modeling of graphene–polymer interfacial mechanical behavior using molecular dynamics, *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, **17**, 2009, pp. 015002 (doi: [10.1088/0965-0393/17/1/015002](https://doi.org/10.1088/0965-0393/17/1/015002)).
- [30] Y. Li and G.D. Seidel, Multiscale modeling of the effects of nanoscale load transfer on the effective elastic properties of unfunctionalized carbon nanotube–polyethylene nanocomposites, *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, **22**, 2014, pp. 025023 (doi: [10.1088/0965-0393/22/2/025023](https://doi.org/10.1088/0965-0393/22/2/025023)).
- [31] M. Li, H. Zhou, Y. Zhang, Y. Liao and H. Zhou, The effect of defects on the interfacial mechanical properties of graphene/epoxy composites, *Rsc Advances*, **7**, 2017, pp. 46101-46108 (doi: [10.1039/c7ra08243f](https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ra08243f)).
- [32] H. Lorenz, M. Despont, N. Fahrni, N. LaBianca, P. Renaud and P. Vettiger, SU-8: a low-cost negative resist for MEMS, *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, **7**, 1997, pp. 121-124 (doi: [10.1088/0960-1317/7/3/010](https://doi.org/10.1088/0960-1317/7/3/010)).
- [33] J. Hammacher, A. Fuele, J. Flaemig, J. Saupe, B. Loechel and J. Grimm, Stress engineering and mechanical properties of SU-8-layers for mechanical applications, *Microsystem Technologies*, **14**, 2008, pp. 1515-1523 (doi: [10.1007/s00542-007-0534-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00542-007-0534-7)).
- [34] R. Feng and R.J. Farris, The characterization of thermal and elastic constants for an epoxy photoresist SU8 coating, *Journal of Materials Science*, **37**, 2002, pp. 4793-4799 (doi: [10.1023/A:1020862129948](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020862129948)).
- [35] C. Li, A.R. Browning, S. Christensen and A. Strachan, Atomistic simulations on multilayer graphene reinforced epoxy composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43**, 2012, pp. 1293-1300 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.02.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.02.015)).
- [36] S. Plimpton, Fast Parallel Algorithms for Short-Range Molecular Dynamics, *Journal of Computational Physics*, **117**, 1995, pp. 1-19 (doi: [10.1006/jcph.1995.1039](https://doi.org/10.1006/jcph.1995.1039)).
- [37] S. Nosé. A Unified Formulation of the Constant Temperature Molecular Dynamics Method, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, **81**, 1984, pp. 511 (doi: [10.1063/1.447334](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.447334)).
- [38] W.G. Hoover, Canonical dynamics: Equilibrium phase-space distributions, *Physical Review A*, **31**, 1985, pp. 1695-1697 (doi: [10.1103/PhysRevA.31.1695](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.31.1695)).
- [39] J.M. Chu, B. Claus, N. Parab, D. O'Brien, T. Sun, K. Fezzaa and W.N. Chen, Visualization of dynamic fiber-matrix interfacial shear debonding, *Journal of Materials Science*, **53**, 2018, pp. 5845-5859 (doi: [10.1007/s10853-017-1759-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-017-1759-1)).
- [40] L.-h. Tam and D. Lau, Effect of structural voids on mesoscale mechanics of epoxy-based materials, *Coupled Systems mechanics*, **5**, 2016, pp. 355-369 (doi: [10.12989/csm.2016.5.4.355](https://doi.org/10.12989/csm.2016.5.4.355)).
- [41] K.H.G. Ashbee and R.C. Wyatt, Water Damage in Glass Fibre/Resin Composites, *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, **312**, 1969, pp. 553-564 (doi: [10.1098/rspa.1969.0175](https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1969.0175)).
- [42] N.R. Farrar and K.H.G. Ashbee, Destruction of epoxy resins and of glass-fibre-reinforced epoxy resins by diffused water, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, **11**, 1978, pp. 1009-1013 (doi: [10.1088/0022-3727/11/6/020](https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/11/6/020)).
- [43] E. Walter and K.H.G. Ashbee, Osmosis in composite materials, *Composites*, **13**, 1982, pp. 365-368 (doi: [10.1016/0010-4361\(82\)90144-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4361(82)90144-6)).